

INVESTIGATING THE AGING STABILITY AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF CHITOSAN-COATED PAPER FOR SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: *Paper is a valuable material in important areas such as printing, packaging, healthcare, food and agriculture. Its ageing process is influenced by storage conditions, microbiological factors and chemical composition. Chitosan, which is compatible with cellulose, is widely used as an additive and coating in paper manufacturing. Understanding the ageing stability of chitosan-coated paper is crucial from a scientific and practical point of view. The aim of this study was to investigate the thermal stability of chitosan-coated woodfree wrapping paper. Pulp and four paper samples were investigated, with three samples coated with different amounts of chitosan. Accelerated thermal ageing at 105°C for 72 hours was performed, along with dynamic thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and evaluation of colour changes. The results showed that higher chitosan coating improved the ageing stability due to improved cross-linking with the paper substrate, resulting in higher strength. Thermogravimetric analysis showed thermal stability improved by 2.6°C with higher chitosan coating. The surface of the coated paper samples appeared more uniform and the barrier properties were improved. The chitosan coating had a positive effect on the ageing stability and thermal properties of wood-free wrapping paper. Its potential as an effective additive and coating in paper production was highlighted. Understanding the relationship between the amount of chitosan, ageing stability and performance characteristics is crucial for the development of sustainable and high-performance paper products in various fields.*

Keywords: bio-based polymers; stability; packaging paper; thermogravimetric analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Green Deal (European Green Deal, 2023) emphasises sustainability, and in this context, paper is an excellent choice for various applications such as packaging, printing and hygiene products thanks to its multiple properties, being recyclable, biodegradable, lightweight and having commendable mechanical properties. However, due to its porous and fibrous structure and limited barrier properties, especially low resistance to oil and grease, challenges arise in packaging (Wang et al., 2022). Attempts have been made to modify the surface with waxes and polymeric coatings, but their impact on the environment raises concerns. To ensure the shelf life of products and prevent contamination during storage and transportation, the integration of antibacterial properties into medical and food packaging is essential. Given the need for environmentally friendly solutions under the European Green Deal, the demand for renewable polysaccharide-based composites is key as they enable packaging improvement, reduce hazardous by-products and promote recycling. Polysaccharides such as cellulose, chitosan, starch etc. play an important role in improving paper coatings. Chitosan, which is derived from chitin, offers beneficial properties such as biodegradability, biocompatibility and non-toxicity, so it is often used as a coating, food additive and antibacterial agent in packaging (Azmana et al., 2021). Chitosan-coated paper improves mechanical, barrier and antimicrobial properties and is a potential replacement for fossil-based packaging (Tanpitchai et al., 2019; Gatto et al., 2019). Namely it fills the pores of paper, reduces water vapour permeability and increases stiffness, strength and toughness (Fernandes et al., 2011; Verma et al., 2019). In addition, researchers have explored chitosan-coated paper for antimicrobial packaging applications (Morin-Crini et al., 2019; Egil et al., 2022). The sensitivity of chitosan to degradation, particularly thermal degradation at temperatures above 200–220°C, has been investigated and plasticisers such as glycerol, xylitol and sorbitol have been explored to mitigate this problem. Important thermal analyses, especially TGA, help to understand and control the processing and working conditions of chitosan-based materials (Xing et al., 2020). Advances in chitosan-based materials include composite and multilayer coatings that combine the mechanical strength of paper with barrier properties (Ezati & Rhim., 2020). This study focuses on investigating the thermal stability of paper coatings with bio-based chitosan and provides valuable insights into the ageing of paper with such coatings as packaging material. The experiment aims to produce chitosan-coated wood-free wrapping paper with different amounts of chitosan and to investigate

its strength and thermal stability over time, contributing to the development of sustainable packaging solutions.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Paper samples

Initially, cellulose mixtures for paper samples were produced from bleached wood-free kraft pulp purchased from Svenska Cellulosa Aktiebolaget (SCA), Sweden, and Svilosa AD, Bulgaria. Pulp grinding was carried out with a laboratory valley beater according to ISO 5264-1:1979. The result was an 80:20 pulp blend with a 30 °SR (Schopper Riegler value) grind according to ISO 5267-1/ AC:2004. The experimental setup included a pure pulp sample, a base paper sample and three chitosan coated paper samples. The base paper was produced using wet chemical additives, including alkyl ketene dimer sizing agents and cationic retention additives. A Rapid-Koethen laboratory paper machine according to ISO 5269-2:2005 with a basis weight of 50 g/m² was used to simulate paper production. The wet paper samples were dried at 95°C and –90 kPa pressure for 7 minutes.

2.2 Coating procedure

The chitosan coating was prepared using Fluka Crayfish Chitosan 28191 dissolved in 1% aqueous acetic acid. The solution was stirred at 300 rpm for 24 hours until the chitosan had completely dissolved and a viscosity of 300 mPa·s was reached. The laboratory base paper samples were coated with chitosan solution and dried in a vacuum dryer at 50°C and 0.08 MPa until completely dry. The coatings obtained had grammages of 0.5 g/m², 1 g/m² and 2 g/m² (Table 1). The coating was applied using the K Control Coater laboratory coating machine, which is equipped with standard wire rods for uniform and repeatable coating application. A stainless steel K-rod with a wire diameter of 1.52 mm was used for wet coating.

Table 1. Samples and used coatings.

Sample	General characteristics
0	Only pulp
1	Base paper
2	Base paper + 0.5 g/m ² chitosan
3	Base paper + 1 g/m ² chitosan
4	Base paper + 2 g/m ² chitosan

3 RESULTS

The smoothness of paper plays a crucial role in achieving an effective surface-coating process and reflects any modifications in the paper surface structure. Based on the data in Table 2, the addition of hydrophobic agent and retention additive does not impact paper surface smoothness (comparing sample 0 to sample 1). The coated paper samples exhibit a denser structure, which increases proportionally with the grammage of the chitosan coating.

Table 2. Sample characteristics of the used materials and coatings.

Paper properties	Testing method	Sample				
		0	1	2	3	4
Grammage (g/m ²)	ISO 536:2012	50.89±2	50.96±2	50.48±3	49.68±3	49.95±3
Thickness (mm)	ISO 534:2011	0.081±0.01	0.081±0.01	0.080±0.01	0.078±0.02	0.079±0.02
Porosity (%)	ISO 534:2011	57.6±0.5	58.06±0.6	57.93±0.8	55.84±0.9	55.60±0.9
Smoothness (Bekk, top side) (s)	ISO 5627:1995	10.98±1.12	10.96±1.19	12.27±1.24	14.56±1.36	16.42±1.93

Figure 1. a) TGA analysis and b) Lightness of the paper samples without and with chitosan-coating during 72 h thermal aging.

The thermal degradation patterns of all studied samples, including the cellulose sample, base paper, and chitosan-coated paper samples, appear identical (Figure 1a). However, sample 3 (base paper + 2 g/m² chitosan) shows a different deviation in weight change, likely attributed to the uneven distribution of chitosan coating, owing to its higher amount relative to the low base paper weight of only 50 g/m².

As seen from Figure 1b, the color coordinate (L^*) of the examined paper samples decreases as expected over time. Small differences between cellulose-only (sample 0) and base paper (sample 1) are observed, but with a comparatively low color parameter variation over time, most pronounced in the first 24 hours of accelerated thermal aging. Adding chitosan-coating slightly darkens the paper but remains close to the base paper. Increasing chitosan-coating from 0.5 g/m² to 2 g/m² and extending thermal aging darkens the paper samples and increases the color difference. The curves' location does not correspond directly to the chitosan-coating amount. Noticeably, paper with 2 g/m² of chitosan-coating (sample 4) exhibits higher whiteness than the other two coated samples (sample 2 and sample 3). This result is likely due to uneven coating distribution and additional cross-linking processes occurring in the chitosan-coating at 105°C. Despite the high temperature during accelerated aging, the lightness reversion from 0 to 72 hours for the three coated papers ranges from 92 to 87, which is relatively low.

The strength properties of paper serve as essential indicators, reflecting its ability to withstand various processing conditions and determining the load resistance of the resulting products. In this reserach, we focus on describing the tensile index and tear index, which are important parameters in assessing the paper's strength characteristics.

Figure 2. Tensile and tear index of analysed samples.

Figure 2 shows the strength properties, indicating that the addition of "wet-end" chemical additives has a positive impact. However, the chitosan coating has a negative effect on the tensile index, likely due to reduced elasticity and plasticity of the base paper. Instead of observing a reduction in tensile index, an increase

of approximately 46.75% is measured with 2 g/m² chitosan coating compared to the base paper, and a 10.30% increase is observed with the lowest chitosan coating (0.5 g/m²). With the increase in chitosan coating on paper from 0.5 g/m² to 2 g/m², the strength indicators show significant improvement at both 0 hours and 72 hours of thermal aging. This enhancement can be attributed not only to the larger coating layer but also to the improved adhesion between the base paper and chitosan layer. Additionally, the crosslinking effect of chitosan at higher thermal aging temperatures is visibly contributing to the observed effect.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Chitosan coating has proven to be a highly effective method for enhancing paper properties and expanding its applications. In our experiments, we tested uncoated and chitosan-coated paper samples made from bleached soft- and hardwood pulp in an 80:20 ratio. The results showed that the coated papers exhibited good strength and thermal stability during 72 hours of accelerated thermal aging. The weight loss of chitosan-coated paper samples was slightly lower than the uncoated base paper. Moreover, the maximum weight loss temperature increased with higher chitosan coating amounts. Interestingly, after aging, an increase of about 46.75% in tensile index at 2 g/m² chitosan coating compared to the base paper and 10.30% at the lowest chitosan coating (0.5 g/m²) was observed. These findings demonstrate the significant benefits of chitosan coating in improving paper properties and suggest its potential for various applications.

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